

Grant Agreement N°653373

SPICY Deliverable D9.2

Communication tools (project identity set, website)

WP	9	Dissemination and exploitation
Task	9.1	Dissemination and Communication

Dissemination level¹	PU	Due delivery date	31/10/2015
Nature²	O	Actual delivery date	02/11/2015

Lead beneficiary	CEA
Contributing beneficiaries	KS

Document Version	Date	Author	Comments ³
vfinal	29/10/2015	Frederic MAZARIN, Kurt Salmon	

¹ Dissemination level: **PU** = Public, **PP** = Restricted to other programme participants (including the JU), **RE** = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the JU), **CO** = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the JU)

² Nature of the deliverable: **R** = Report, **P** = Prototype, **D** = Demonstrator, **O** = Other

³ Creation, modification, final version for evaluation, revised version following evaluation, final

Deliverable abstract

This deliverable contains the logo, as well as explanations, going along with screenshots, about the different sections to be found into the released SPICY website

www.spicy-project.eu

Deliverable Review

Reviewer #1: Willy Porcher.....			Reviewer #2: Willy PORCHER		
Answer	Comments	Type*	Answer	Comments	Type*
1. Is the deliverable in accordance with					
(i) the Description of Work?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a	X Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a
(ii) the international State of the Art?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a	X Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a
2. Is the quality of the deliverable in a status					
(i) that allows it to be sent to European Commission?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a	X Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a
(ii) that needs improvement of the writing by the originator of the deliverable?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes X No		<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a
(iii) that needs further work by the Partners responsible for the deliverable?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes X No		<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a

* Type of comments: M = Major comment; m = minor comment; a = advice

Table of content

1. Introduction	4
2. Website structure	4
3. SPICY logo and website	4
4. Conclusion	5

1. Introduction

The SPICY project website has been released by Kurt Salmon and will be maintained with general project information, project results, relevant news, consortium members, and information on the status and activities organized by the partners. Public documents generated by the project will also be available on the website. The Management team will prepare an editorial plan in order to update continuously the web site with the contributions of all partners.

2. Website structure

Figure 1: SPICY website breakdown

3. SPICY logo and website

The SPICY logo (see below) has been chosen by the General Assembly via vote.

Figure 2: SPICY logo

Figure 3: SPICY website homepage

The SPICY website address is:

www.spicy-project.eu

In the SPICY website, the homepage gives a short overview of the project and the last news regarding the project (conference attendances, last released public reports etc).

Deeper explanation and links to specific results are displayed in the “About the project” page. The members of the project are presented in a specific “Partners”. The SPICY website will inform the public about the latest results found for the project development and about the progress of the project steps.

A specific page “news and results” in the website will be dedicated to the diffusion of the project results. Also, the main new results and highlights will be published in the “news” category in order to give an easy and regular access to these information about the project progression. This page will be regularly updated.

A specific contact page is also to be found in order to give the possibility to interested people to interact with the SPICY team and ask questions, to learn more about the SPICY technologies and exploitation possibilities, taking part in dissemination activities, contribute to the project or even meet SPICY partners to conferences.

4. Conclusion

The SPICY website will be updated on a regular basis under the responsibility of CEA to ensure it provides information adapted for specific target groups, including researchers, students, future customers and investors. The participation of partners at events as well as the SPICY workshop will also be advertised ahead of time on the site.